

Experiments with random star distributions

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To generate a star field with constant areal density but with varying degree of "regularity", one can use the following method. Start with a regular mesh, i.e. a completely regular star field with separation D between adjacent stars (Fig. 1). Then imagine a square of size $wD \times wD$ centred on each mesh point, generate a star with uniform probability density inside that square, and repeat for next mesh point. Depending on the parameter w , the resulting star field can be anything from completely regular ($w = 0$, Fig. 1) to completely random, i.e. each star independently and uniformly distributed ($w = \infty$, Fig. 7).

The regularity of any two-dimensional point distribution can be estimated e.g. by means of the function

$$q(r) = (\langle n^2 \rangle - \langle n \rangle^2) / \langle n \rangle \quad (1)$$

where n = number of points inside an arbitrarily centred circle of radius r . If n is Poisson distributed, we have $q(r) = 1$ for all r ; for a regular mesh, $q(r) \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$. For simplicity we may consider only $Q \equiv q(D)$, where $D = (\text{areal density})^{-1/2}$. For the quadratic mesh in Fig. 1,

$$Q = \frac{17}{3} - \pi - (4 + 2\sqrt{3})/\pi \approx 0.14918 \quad (2)$$

Comments to the Figures:

- Fig. 1 - 3: The underlying mesh is easily discerned up to $w \approx 0.5$. The number Q computed for these Figures (by averaging over 100 circles) are not significantly different from (2).
- Fig. 4: With $w = 1$, the mesh is invisible but the distribution still appears to be abnormally "uniform". This is confirmed by the computed $Q = 0.28$.
- Fig. 5 - 6: With $w = 2$ to 4, the distribution appears completely random, but Q is still significantly below 1 ($Q = 0.64 - 0.78$).
- Fig. 7: This is the truly uncorrelated distribution ($w = \text{infinity}$). $Q = 1$ in theory, slightly more as computed for the actual distribution in this Figure.
- Fig. 8: This Figure was generated to give a strong tendency for clustering, using a quite different method than described above. $Q = 2.5$.

For HIPPARCOS Input Catalogue it is perhaps realistic to expect a typical distribution similar to Fig. 5 ($w = 2$, $Q = 0.64$).

$w = 0$

$q = 0.15$

Figure 1

$w = 0.3$

$q = 0.15$

Figure 2

$w = 0.5$

$q = 0.16$

Figure 3

$w = 1.0$

$q = 0.28$

Figure 4

$w = 2$

$q = 0.64$

Figure 5

$w = 4$

$q = 0.78$

Figure 6

$w = \text{INFINITE}$

$q = 1.1$

Figure 7

CLUSTERING

$q = 2.5$

Figure 8